

UAS proximal remote sensing for complex ancient quarries 3D documentation

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Abstract

The documentation of ancient quarries is often very critical due to the complexity of the archaeological sites. In this paper we discuss a method based on proximal sensing photogrammetry technique, to obtain detailed survey by means of an Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS). This technique allows to acquire high definition digital images to generate, by means of semi-automatic photogrammetric algorithms, very dense point clouds and Digital Surface Model. The method based on UAS platforms allows to perform survey also in hazardous areas with reliability and safety, in order to obtain metrological data from 3D reconstruction of quarry sites. The proximal sensing survey was performed at different flight heights, according to the ground sample distance (GSD) needed to generate DSM by the combination of different photogrammetric shots at consistent resolutions. The flight planning is another very important step, that must consider steep or tall quarry walls and the variable exposition to the incident light, in order to minimize the errors on digital models and to obtain more detailed representation. This method allows to investigate on stone exploitation technology, volumes of the materials exploited and debris accumulation, geometrical and dimensional characteristics of the stone artefacts production. With approach we can also evaluate the archaeological heritage interactions with the environmental processes, as support of conservative and valorization projects.

Keywords. UAS, Proximal Sensing, 3D modeling, Photogrammetry, Ancient Quarries

1 Introduction

The aim of this work is to propose a methodological approach for proximal survey technique with UAS system for 3D detailed photogrammetric documentation of ancient quarries and stone artefacts, which could then be applied to other similar sites of interest. This technique allows to collect high definition digital images to generate very dense point clouds for DSM elaboration, particularly suited for quarry fronts, pillars and columns reconstruction.

This study is focused on a Roman quarry area in Northern Sardinia, where pink/greyish granitic rocks have been used for column and pillars production. This area preserves some well known ancient stone quarries of the early second Century AD, when the trade of these materials interested the Imperial Rome and several Roman Provinces of the Mediterranean basin [1]-[10]-[13]. The dating of these quarries is supported by the archaeological investigation carried out on the vicinity of the Capo Testa area, particularly at the Santa Reparata bay, where a large quantity of pottery fragments and burials have been related to the mid-second Century AD [2].

In this work have been investigated several small quarries of Capo Testa and namely the *loci* of Cala Romana, Li Petri Taddati, where was previously performed a geoarchaeological survey, rock sampling and classification [1].

The detailed survey of these areas is a real challenge due to the very complex morphology and difficult access. The quarries often show vertical walls, lot of rock debris and unfinished artefacts, which require an appropriate and accurate survey method to allow a detailed mapping of the different surfaces and forms [4]-[6].

The proposed technique, based on UAS proximal sensing, allows to collect high definition digital images and generate very dense point clouds. In the field of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (PaRS; [7]) the acquisition based on UAS platforms allows to perform very quick survey with reliability and safety, obtaining a better information on morphologically complex surfaces and better accuracy of 3D models [6]. The UAS system used for this purpose is a multirotor drone equipped with two high resolution digital camera and 50mm and 28mm fixed focal lens. The proximal sensing survey was performed at different flight heights (from 3 to 50m), according to the needed ground resolution (GSD), in order to generate DSM by the combination of different photogrammetric shots at consistent resolutions. This procedure reduces errors of digital models due to interpolation, especially in presence of strong steepness, giving a more detailed DSM.

In this paper we report on some results obtained using the proposed method for the modeling of quarry surfaces and artefact fragments that allowed to define the orientation of cracks and cutting edges, the reconstruction of some fragmented columns and the definition of several dimensional parameters. The application of this method allowed the 3D modeling of the ancient quarry archaeological landscape, by using the original elements still in place.

2 UAS photogrammetric survey and equipment for proximal sensing

The survey was performed after the planning several proximity flights, for the characterization of the quarry walls and the identification of specific geometric elements as pillars and column fragments.

The experimental method uses planned flights based on waypoint grids at fixed altitude, for zenithal photos acquisition, and waypoint grids at different altitudes for convergent axis photo acquisition, in order to interest all the inclined surfaces. In this way we can represent all the different surfaces and objects on the quarry and their relative orientation. The flights were performed at different heights ranging from 3 to 50m to obtain high resolution digital surface models by the combination of different photogrammetric shots at consistent high resolutions over Cala Romana e Li Petri Taddati quarry areas (Fig. 1-2).

The UAS used for the survey is an experimental multirotor, based on HiSystems GmbH [8] electronic components (Flight Controller, Navigation controller and GPS module), with a remote Ground Station control unit. The UAS platform was equipped with a Canon 5D MARK II camera and 50 mm and Canon EOS-M 28mm fixed focal lenses. The different altitudes of the photogrammetric flights have been defined taking into account the needed ground sample distance according to the 50mm and

28mm fixed focal length lenses in use (Tab. 1).

Fig. 1 Capo Testa, aerial view of Cala Romana: quarry steps, debris and some column fragments.

Fig. 2 Aerial view of Li Petri Taddati: quarry steps, debris, ashlars, pillars and a

rough column still in place on the cutting step.

The flights were carried out automatically following the way-point grids previously defined according to the general photogrammetric rules (longitudinal overlap >75% and cross-overlap >=50%; Tab. 1-2; Fig. 3). The very first flight was done at the maximum altitude of 50m in order to guarantee a complete coverage of the whole quarry area. The other flights have been realized at different levels from 3 to 10m in order to obtain more detailed shots.

The flight planning is a very important phase, especially when the surfaces that have to be modeled show, as in this case, different material characteristics, strong steepness and different exposition to the incident light (shadows). During the flights it is very important to take the shots always with a convergent axis to the subject. Any combination of shots whether in stereo pairs, stereo triples, strips, sub-blocks or blocks, is handled by forming the set of observation [6]. Furthermore the use of UAS platform allowed to avoid the traditional by hand photo capture near the ground, performing some very low-altitude flights (3-10m) using GPS flight log. The total number of photos captured is 410.

Tab. 1 Flight planning parameters

Survey*	GSD (cm/pixel)	Sensor Type (CANON)	Focal length (mm)	Flying Altitude (m)	Elaborated Area (mq)	α (°)	Waypoints WP (num.)	V (m/s)	Images (num.)	GCPs (num.)	RMSE CPs (pixel)
CR1	1,05	EOS M	28	50	3750	0°	16	3	160	12	0,44
LP1	1,12	EOS M	28	50	2250	0°	16	3	160	12	0,52

(*) CR = Cala Romana - LP = Li Petri Taddati

Survey*	GSD (cm/pixel)	Sensor Type (CANON)	Focal length (mm)	Flying Altitude (m)	Elaborated Area (mq)	α (°)	Waypoints WP (num.)	V (m/s)	Images (num.)	GCPs (num.)	RMSE CPs (pixel)
CR3	0,15	5D Mark II	50	3-10	405	0°-72°	9x4	1	36	6	0,35
CR2	0,04	EOS M	28	3-10	285	0°-72°	9x3	1	27	6	1,12
LP2	0,03	EOS M	28	3-10	290	0°-72°	9x3	1	27	6	1,01

(*) CR = Cala Romana - LP = Li Petri Taddati

Tab. 2 Features of the UAS platform

GPS* Accuracy (m)	Diameter UAV (m)	UAV weight (gr)	Power supply Li-Po	Pay-load Take-off (gr)	Radius range (m)	Altitude range (m)	Flight time (min)	Camera CANON	Sensor type (Mpixel)	CCD Matrix (pixel)	Focal length** (mm)
2	1	3450	2x5300 mAh 14,8 V	1150	250	3-10	3-10	5D Mark II	21	5616x3744	50
2	1	3450	2x5300 mAh 14,8 V	550	250	3-50	3-10	EOS M	18	5184x3456	28

(*) GPS positioning NEO M8N UBLOX

(**) Lens calibration: Focal length (f_x, f_y), Principal point (c_x, c_y), K1, K2, K3, P1, P2 - RMSE 0.098 pixel

Fig. 3 Waipoint flight planning: Cala Romana (left), Li Petri Taddati quarries (right).

The final step of our work was collecting the ground control points (GCPs). The GCPs were collected with an accuracy of RMSE measurements <2.0cm using a Topcon RTK-GPS receiver. For this purpose a local geodetic control network were first established by a few GCP markers, used as main control points and positioned in WGS84 coordinates (World Geodetic System, 1984). A total of 42 GCPs was collected in order to compare the oriented photogrammetric data coordinates with the

corresponding ground survey data. This set of ground control points was imported into Capturing Reality photogrammetric software [3], where it was integrated to the coordinate system of the flights.

Fig. 4 Geometric representation of rules adopted for the photogrammetric flights: G1 - zenithal waypoints grid; G2 - convergent waypoints grid.

3 Data processing and 3D modeling

Although the natural landscape is always more complex than any computer representation, and the purpose of most modelers is not a photorealistic representation, the use of 3D reconstruction is changing, along with its successful integration and evolution of new tools to represent and explore landscapes.

During the last years, in the field of close-range (proximal) photogrammetry, the techniques of automatic aerial triangulation have been improved. According to Verhoeven [11] for a good 3D reconstruction the photos must be taken as perpendicular as possible to the investigated surfaces/object. For data elaboration we used the algorithm supported by Capturing Reality software [3], that shows very good performance for DSM generation in terms of process speed and ease of use with heterogeneous structured datasets. It's very interesting to see how easily new aerial images can be added or deleted at any time of the elaboration process to obtain a better geo-referenced orthomosaic and/or a best resolution of DSM and 3D model. The DMS surfaces were reconstructed using an automatic procedure, generating very dense point clouds (Fig. 5-6-7). In this work we have carried out some detailed models of the ancient quarries showing the cutting steps, ashlar, pillars, columns and

debris accumulation. The result of this elaboration is a very good geometrical representation with RGB values extracted from the photos, giving to the textured point clouds a realistic appearance [5]. Some editing of points and mesh have been required after automated processing to fill some “holes” and to remove boundary errors. The point clouds have been optimized with MeshLab V1.3.3 [9] processing software using advanced algorithms. The software assigned the spatial coordinates (x, y, z) and the true-color information (RGB) for each pixel in order to generate a fully textured 3D model reconstruction of the investigated area. Finally we have carried out a realistic 3D digital reconstruction with Rhinoceros V5.0 [12] to elaborate the 3D models (Fig. 8-9) and calculate volumes of exploited materials, debris accumulation, geometrical and dimensional characteristics of the stone artefacts production.

Fig. 5 Cala Romana quarry: point cloud model (left); low flight aerial photo (right)

Fig. 6 Li petri Taddati quarry: point cloud models (left); aerial photo (right)

Fig. 7 Li Petri Taddati quarry, Screenshot from low flight representation: a zenithal view (left) and convergent view point cloud model (right)

Fig. 8 3D photogrammetric reconstruction of a column and details of its parts.

Fig. 9 3D photogrammetric reconstruction Li Petri Taddati quarry steps: A1: rough column fragment on step; B1: quarry step; B2: preparation cuts; C: simulated column shape on ancient step.

4 Conclusion

This work aimed at the optimization and evaluation of a method for proximal remote sensing using a UAS multirotor platform, to document archaeological sites through 3D modeling representation. The proposed method is not expensive, it is reliable,

quick, accurate and safe. It is also particularly suited for morphological complex sites, with low vegetation cover, and wherever the survey concerns hazardous areas. The combination of UAS photogrammetric proximal survey and 3D digital reconstruction is very useful for archaeological landscape assessment, quarry surfaces and stone artefacts. The development of our research will provide the survey of the other Roman quarries of Capo Testa in order to complete the digital documentation with DSM, DTM, orthophotos and textured 3D models. The data analysis carried out with the application of this experimental method is the essential background for more exhaustive studies. This method results more effective if associated with GIS technology application becoming a powerful and sophisticated integrated method to investigate on stone exploitation technology, estimation of exploited volumes and quantity of debris accumulation, geometrical and dimensional characteristics of the stone artefacts production. This method is also a useful tool to evaluate the archaeological heritage interactions with environmental processes, as support of conservative and valorization projects.

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